

NANOCOMPOSITES FOR POWER LAMINATES

H. S. Kim¹, Y. M. Lee³, S. Dhage¹, J. S. Kang¹ and H. T. Hahn^{1,2*}

¹Mechanical and Aerospace Engineering Department

²Material Science and Engineering Department

²California NanoSystems Institute

University of California, Los Angeles, CA 90095, USA

³I/E Materials R&D Center, SK Energy, Daejeon, Korea

hahn@seas.ucla.edu

SUMMARY

Power laminates which can harvest and store the energy are being developed using nanocomposites. A copper nanoink is used to print electrode patterns on a power laminate using an inkjet printer. CIG and Se nanoparticles are used to fabricate a thin-film CIGS solar cell directly on the composite laminate. A thin film Li-ion battery is fabricated using nanocomposite electrodes. A power laminate consisting of a thin-film solar cell and a thin-film battery electrically connected via inkjet-printed circuits is fabricated and tested to show the need to develop more flexible thin-film solar cells and thin-film batteries.

Keywords: Energy harvesting and storage laminate, nanoink, multifunctional composite, inkjet printed electronics, thin-film solar cell, thin-film batteries

1. Introduction

There is much interest in the development of unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) which has autonomous power supply, i.e., self energy harvesting and storage capability [1]. However, most energy harvesting and storage systems are parasitic to load bearing structure, thereby increasing the total weight and volume of the system and decreasing the fuel efficiency and payload. Therefore, recently, multifunctional composite structures have been developed by embedding thin-film photovoltaic [2] and energy-storage [3] devices into composite laminates having multifunctional capabilities, thereby saving the weight and volume. However, the research results about the direct fabrication of the photo-voltaic and energy-storage components on the composite laminate are rare to author's knowledge. Also, there has been no attempt to integrate solar cells and batteries together into a load bearing structure.

In this paper, the power laminate which can harvest and store the energy, was developed using nano composite materials. A copper nano ink was used to lay down an electrode pattern on a power laminate using ink jet printing method. Molybdenum, CIGS, CdS nano composite inks were prepared and printed by screen printing method to fabricate the CIGS solar cell directly on the power laminate. In order to sinter the printed conductive paths and the solar cell layers in room temperature and ambient condition, an intense pulsed light sintering technique was newly introduced. Also, the thin film Li-ion battery was fabricated and integrated into the composite laminate for

energy storage purpose using carbon nano tube and silicon nano composite materials. Toward developing such a full power laminate, we demonstrate the use of an inkjet printing method to lay down the required conducting circuits with commercial a thin-film solar cell and a thin-film battery integrated into a graphite/epoxy composite laminate. Finally, the structural and functional performance of the power laminate is investigated under mechanical loading.

2.1 Ink jet printing of copper electrodes

A copper nanoink was used to print the conductive path for a power laminate. The copper nanoink has copper particles 5 nm in diameter uniformly dispersed in a mixed solvent of ethylene glycol and 2-methoxyethanol (Samsung Electro-Mechanics, Korea). The printing was done on a woven glass fabric/BT (bismaleimide triazine) laminate, called the BT core 0.1 mm thick, using an inkjet print head mounted on a computer-controlled three-axis gantry system with a movement accuracy of $\pm 1 \mu\text{m}$, Fig. 1.

Fig. 1 Drop-on demand piezoelectric inkjet nozzle: (a) schematic diagram; (c) inkjet printing system.

Fig. 2 Inkjet-printed copper electrode: (a) scratch test result; (b) optical microscope image; (c) tensile test of the printed electrode; (d) 4-wire Kelvin resistance measurement.

After printing, the copper nanoparticles were sintered at 200°C in N_2 gas to prevent oxidation for 20 min. The adhesion between the printed copper electrode and BT core substrate was found to be good from the scratch test using a diamond tip, Fig. 2 (a). Also, the resulting copper electrode has contiguous grain structure, Fig. 2 (b), which

reveals good sintering of nanoparticles. The measured resistivity is about $5 \mu\Omega \text{ cm}$, which is only 3 times higher than that of a typical bulk copper pattern ($1.7 \mu\Omega \text{ cm}$). The higher resistivity may be the result of many pores between necking structure of the sintered copper particles in the printed electrode as shown in SEM microscope of Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. Scanning electron microscope (SEM) image of printed copper electrode.

The change of resistance with tensile strain is shown for electrodes with 4 different thicknesses in Figs. 2 (c) and (d). The resistance decreases with increasing thickness more rapidly than expected as a result of the electrode quality: the thicker the better. Nevertheless, the printed electrodes function well even up to a tensile strain of 1% if they are not too thin ($<4 \mu\text{m}$), Fig. 4. Thus the inkjet printing with copper nanoparticles can be used to print conducting lines on a multifunctional energy harvesting/storage structure.

Fig. 4 Resistances of 160- μm wide printed electrodes with different thicknesses: (a) thickness effect; (b) percentages of resistance change

2.2 CIGS solar cell fabrication by printing technique

The CIGS (copper, indium, gallium, diselenide) solar cell is one of the most efficient thin-film solar cells with the reported efficiency of about 19%, Fig. 5. Therefore, a method is being developed to fabricate CIGS solar cells directly on the power laminate.

Fig. 5. CIGS solar cell: (a) schematic diagram of CIGS solar cell structure; (b) band gap diagram.

Fig. 6. Fabrication process of the CIGS film from the CIG and selenium nano particles using the doctor's blade method followed by the intense pulsed light sintering technique.

As a first step, nanoink was prepared dispersing a mixture of CIG and selenium nanoparticle, which are about 10 nm in diameter, in a mixed solvent of polyethylene glycol (2 wt%) and de-ionized water (98 wt%). The prepared inks were spread on a glass substrate by the doctor's blade method, Fig. 6. An intense pulsed light (IPL) from a xenon lamp was then used to reactively sinter the nanoparticles into a CIGS film, Fig. 7 (a). The X-ray diffraction data shows the appearance of CIGS peaks well in agreement with the reference spectrum, Fig. 7 (b). The CIGS film is now being combined with the other layers to fabricate a thin-film solar cell.

Fig. 7. IPL sintered CIGS film prepared from CIG and Se nanoparticles: (a) SEM image; (b) XRD pattern.

2.3 Thin-film Li-ion battery for power laminate

For the energy storage function of the power laminate, a thin-film Li-ion battery has been developed. Fig. 8 (a) shows a schematic of a composite laminate with the embedded battery. The cathode is a composite of LiMn_2O_4 /Carbon black/PVDF, and the anode, the same composite but with LiMn_2O_4 replace by micro carbon beads. The corresponding current collectors are 30-um thick aluminum and copper films, respectively. Both electrodes were placed in vacuum chamber at 100 °C for 1 hour to completely dry the NMP (N-methylpyrrolidone) solvent. The electrodes and the separator (20-um thick porous polyolefin film) were immersed in the pre-made electrolyte of 1M LiPF_6 /EC (Ethylene carbonate)/DEC (Diethyl carbonate)/PC (Propylene carbonate)/VC (Vinylene carbonate) (Ukseong Chemical, Korea) for 12 h in a glove box. The layers were stacked together as shown in Fig. 8 (b) and sealed by PVC (polyvinyl chloride)/Aluminum/PVC sealing layers, Fig. 8 (c).

Fig. 8. Thin film Li-ion battery: (a) schematic diagram of the embedded battery into load bearing composite laminate; (b) battery inner structure; (c) sealed battery.

The charge and discharge characteristics of the battery itself are shown in Fig. 9 to be fairly good until the 10th recharge cycle. Currently, the thin-film battery is being integrated into a composite laminate and will be tested under various mechanical loading conditions such as tensile, bending and shear loading.

Fig. 9. The battery energy capacities: (a) charging curve; (b) discharging curve; (c) energy capacity with respect to re-charging cycle.

2.4 Fabrication of an energy harvesting/storage laminate

An energy harvesting/storage composite laminate was made using inkjet-printed electrodes as interconnections between an amorphous Si thin-film solar cell, Table 1, and a lithium thin-film battery, Table 2. Fig. 10 (a) shows the inkjet-printed circuits to connect the solar cell and the battery on a BT core (0.1 mm thickness). The electrodes on the top and bottom surfaces are connected to each other through via-holes by smearing the nanoink into them followed by sintering. In order to insulate the electrodes from graphite fibers in the composite, a polyimide ink was printed and cured with a thickness of 25 μm over the whole area of the laminate except where the solar cell and battery are to be located, as shown in Fig. 10 (b).

Fig. 10. Power laminate fabrication: (a) printed electrode pattern with thin film solar cell and battery; (d) cross-sectional view of the co-cured power laminate.

Table 1 Specification of the amorphous silicon thin-film solar cell

Part number	TX3-25
Manufacturer	Powerfilm Inc.
Typical Voc (V), Isc (mA)	4.2 V, 35 mA
Total size (mm)	114 x 25
Total thickness (mm)	0.2
Weight (g)	0.8

Table 2 Specification of the lithium thin-film battery

Company (Part number)	Front Edge Technology (S8-ES)
Operating voltage (V)	4
Capacity (mAh)	0.42
Total size (mm)	25.4 x 25.4
Total thickness (μm)	114
Weight (g)	0.2

The final assembly consisting of the BT core, the solar cell and the battery was co-cured on a graphite/epoxy laminate (T700SC/RS-30G) with the lay-up sequence of $[0/90]_s$ in an autoclave at 120 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 2 h. Figure 9 (c) shows a cross section of the power laminate. The maximum thickness of the specimen was 0.99 mm including 0.67mm for the graphite/epoxy composite. The power laminate had almost the same strength and modulus as the composite laminate by itself, as expected.

Fig. 11 Experimental setup of the integrated power laminate: (a) schematic diagram; (b) sectional view of the power laminate.

Figure 11 shows the experimental set-up to test the performance of the power laminate under mechanical loading. The light was shone on the solar cell using an overhead projector. The current-voltage (I-V) relationships of the solar cell were measured using a source meter. From the obtained I-V curve, the fill factor is calculated as follows:

$$FF = \frac{MPP}{I_{SC} \times V_{OC}} \quad (1)$$

where, I_{SC} , V_{OC} and MPP are the short circuit current, the open circuit voltage and the maximum power, respectively.

The I-V curves and fill factors of the solar cell in the power laminate at different strain levels are shown in Fig. 12. Both of them hardly change up to 1% strain, which is similar to the result of Sugar et al. [2]. Figure 13 shows the battery's charge-discharge characteristics. For the charge cycle, a constant voltage of 4.2 V is applied until the current drops to 0.1 mA. For the discharge cycle, the current is maintained at 1 mA until the voltage drops to 3 V. The charge and discharge capacities are then calculated by integrating the measured current over time to the cut-off point. The performance of battery itself, is seen to degrade drastically at about 0.45% strain, Fig. 13, which is similar to the result of Pereira et al. [3]. The 0.45% strain for the battery failure might be too low for power laminates. Thus a need exists to develop thin-film batteries which are more flexible.

Fig. 12 Performance of the solar cell and battery in the power laminate under mechanical loading: (a) I-V curve of the solar cell with respect to static strain; (b) fill factor of solar cell.

Fig. 13 The battery charge/discharge capacity under tensile loading.

Fig. 14 shows the current and voltage measured during the battery charging by the solar cell at no strain and at 0.4% strain. In both cases, the battery was charged from a fully discharged state. No effect of strain is seen in the figure. Therefore, it could be concluded that the energy harvested by the solar cell could be stored to the embedded battery successfully through the inkjet-printed electrical connections on the power laminate at a tensile strain of up to 0.4%.

Fig. 14 Charging characteristics of the battery from the solar cell in the power laminate at no strain and 0.4 % of static strain.

3. Conclusions

We have demonstrated the use of various types of nanocomposites to develop a power laminate. A copper nanoink was used to print an electrode pattern on a power laminate. A colloidal solution containing CIG and CdS nanoparticles was used to

fabricate a CIGS solar cell through the intense pulsed light sintering in ambient conditions. A thin film Li-ion battery was also fabricated using composite electrodes. As a first step toward developing a power laminate, a commercially available thin-film solar cell and a thin-film battery were integrated into a graphite/epoxy composite laminate and were electrically connected via inkjet-printed electrodes. The I-V curve of the solar cell does not change much up to the applied tensile strain of 1% while the battery's charge/discharge capacity is drastically degraded at 0.45% strain. Thus there is a need to develop more flexible solar cells and batteries if multifunctional power laminates are to be realized.

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